

Impact of Shifting China-U.S Strategic Dynamics on Pakistan's Geopolitical Positioning

Maimoona Rasool

Assistant professor, National University of Computer & Emerging Sciences, Islamabad

PhD scholar National Institute of Pakistan studies, Quaid e Azam University Islamabad

maimoona.rasool@nu.edu.pk

***Abstract:** The development of Pakistan's ties with both China and the United States identify crucial turning points and contextualizing them within emerging global power dynamics. It focuses on U.S. primacy and Chinese growing assertiveness, examining Pakistan's role in the evolving geostrategic environment. The problem of this research is to understand how the intensifying U.S.-China rivalry influences Pakistan's economy, security and regional standing, particularly in light of key projects like the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). The paper try to find to answer the following questions How does the U.S.-China rivalry shape Pakistan's strategic decisions and influence its economic cooperation, regional stability and geopolitical positioning? This question is explored through an extensive review of existing literature, with recent works by Zhao and Liu (2024) and Ahmed and Khan (2023) providing essential insights into the ongoing dynamics. However, there remains a gap in understanding how these shifts specifically affect Pakistan. The research employs Realism as its theoretical framework, drawing on the works of Mearsheimer, which emphasizes power*

competition and strategic interests. to analyze how states struggle for power in an anarchic international system. The research offers nuanced insights into the real-world consequences of major power rivalry on Pakistan's economic cooperation, regional stability and geopolitical positioning, providing valuable guidance for strategic decision-making in this complex environment.

Keywords: *Geostrategic environment, U.S.-China rivalry, Regional stability, Realism, CPEC, Power dynamics*

Introduction

The interactions among major global powers significantly shape the geopolitical landscape. At this time, the ongoing rivalry between China and the United States exerts considerable influence and within this complex strategic environment, Pakistan circumnavigate an elusive balance between its historical alliances and the evolving demands of contemporary geopolitics (Anam et al., 2022). The course of Pakistan's relationships with both China and the United States has experienced notable shifts, influenced by a series of events and a web of complicated geopolitical factors (Anwar, 2020). Analyzing this historical evolution is crucial for comprehending the current geopolitical context. This paper aims to explore the changing dynamics of Pakistan's relations with the US and China, providing a deeper understanding of the present geopolitical scenario.

The strategic competition between China and the United States has significantly altered the global geostrategic scenery, with far-reaching implications for regional stability and power dynamics. Pakistan, located at the intersection of South Asia, Central Asia and the Middle East, finds itself at the crossroads of this intensifying rivalry. The evolving power struggle between China and the United States is not merely a bilateral contest but one that has profound consequences for

countries like Pakistan, whose foreign policy and external pressures and internal necessities increasingly shape security strategies. This paper explores the ramifications of the dynamic strategies adopted by China and the United States on Pakistan, with particular emphasis on the geostrategic environment, U.S.-China rivalry and regional stability, realism as a theoretical framework, the China- Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and the broader power dynamics at play.

The geostrategic environment in which Pakistan operates is characterized by a complicated interaction of regional and global powers. The rivalry between China and the United States has introduced new dimensions to this environment, with both powers vying for influence over key regions, including South Asia. The United States, traditionally a dominant player in South Asia, has sought to maintain its influence by strengthening ties with India, Pakistan's neighbor and historical rival. This strategic partnership is part of a broader U.S. strategy to counter China's increasing influence in the Indo-Pacific region. On the other side, China has deepened its strategic and economic links with Pakistan and looking the country as a key partner of its Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) particularly through the development of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). The CPEC, a flagship project of the BRI, has transformed Pakistan's geostrategic importance, making it a focal point of China's ambitions to expand its influence across Asia and beyond. This development has not gone unnoticed by the United States that interpret CPEC as a challenge to its own strategic benefits in the region. The U.S.- China rivalry has thus placed Pakistan in a precarious position, as it directs the competing demands and expectations of both superpowers. The strategic decisions made by Pakistan in this context are shaped by a need to balance these external pressures while safeguarding its own national interests. This balancing act has significant implications for regional stability, as Pakistan's choices could either exacerbate tensions or contribute to a more stable regional order.

The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is a central element of the broader power dynamics between China and the United States. As a key component of China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), CPEC aims to develop connection between China and the Arabian Sea to provide a strategic position to China in the Indian Ocean region. For Pakistan, CPEC represents a major opportunity to address its economic challenges, through infrastructure development and increased foreign investment. However, CPEC is not merely an economic project; it is also a strategic initiative with significant geopolitical implications. The development of Gwadar Port, in particular, has raised concerns in the United States and India about Chinese aims in the region. The location of the port and close to the Strait of Hormuz is a critical chokepoint for global oil supplies that provides China a strategic advantage in securing its energy needs and projecting power in the Indian Ocean. The power dynamics surrounding CPEC are further complicated by the United States' efforts to counter Chinese influence in this region. The U.S. has expressed concerns about the lack of transparency and sustainability of CPEC projects, warning that they could lead to a debt trap for Pakistan. These concerns are part of a broader U.S. strategy to challenge China's Belt and Road Initiative, which it views as a means of expanding Chinese influence at the overhead of other regional powers. Pakistan's role in these power dynamics is shaped by its need to balance its strategic partnership with China against the risks of alienating the United States. While CPEC offers Pakistan significant economic benefits, it also comes with geopolitical risks, as Pakistan becomes increasingly drawn into the broader U.S.-China rivalry. This has led to a elusive balancing act, as Pakistan seeks to maintain its strategic autonomy while avoiding the pitfalls of over-reliance on either power (Ali, 2020).

Theoretical structure

The geopolitical environment of South Asia, with Pakistan at its core, has been profoundly shaped by the evolving strategic rivalry between China and the United States. This rivalry, often analyzed through the lens of international relations theories, particularly realism and liberalism, offers significant insights into the dynamics that influence Pakistan's foreign policy and regional stability. This theoretical framework aims to dissect the ramifications of the U.S.-China strategic competition on Pakistan, employing realism as the primary analytical tool while integrating liberalism to understand the complexities of Sino-Pakistani relations. Realism, a dominant theory in international relations, provides a crucial framework for understanding Pakistan's foreign policy behavior amid the U.S.-China rivalry. Rooted in the notion that the international system is anarchic and that states are inherently self-interested actors seeking survival and power, realism posits that Pakistan's strategic decisions are driven by the need to secure its sovereignty and maintain a balance of power in a region marked by intense rivalry, particularly with India (Waltz, 1979).

From a realist perspective, Pakistan's alignment with China through initiatives like the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is a strategic maneuver to counterbalance India's growing influence, bolstered by its partnership with the United States. According to realists, "States form alliances primarily to enhance their security and power" especially in an anarchic international system where no central authority guarantees state survival (Mearsheimer, 2001). For Pakistan, aligning with China serves as a counterweight to India's military modernization and strategic ties with the U.S., which Pakistan perceives as direct threats to its security (Ain, May 24,

2023). The realist perspective further explains that Pakistan's deepening ties with China are not merely based on economic cooperation but are rooted in shared security concerns. As India's military capabilities and regional assertiveness grow, Pakistan views China as a crucial ally to maintain regional parity. This partnership, from a realist standpoint, is a calculated move to prevent India from achieving regional hegemony, thereby ensuring Pakistan's strategic survival (Mendelson, March 20, 2014).

Realism also sheds light on the security dilemmas and potential for conflict that arise from the U.S.-China rivalry in South Asia. The construction of CPEC through the disputed region of Gilgit-Baltistan, which India claims as its territory, has exacerbated tensions between India and Pakistan. Realists would argue that this development heightens the security dilemma, where actions taken by one state to increase its security (e.g., Pakistan's partnership with China) are perceived as threats by another state (e.g., India), leading to an arms race and increased instability (Jervis, 1978). Moreover, the growing strategic partnership between the United States and India further complicates Pakistan's security environment. The U.S. sees India as a counterbalance to China's influence in Asia, which aligns with India's strategic interests but simultaneously isolates Pakistan (Pant, 2012). In response, Pakistan deepens its reliance on China, reinforcing the security dilemma in the region (Siddique, 2021).

Realism posits that such dynamics are almost inevitable in an anarchic international system where states prioritize their security and survival, often at the expense of regional stability. While the realist approach emphasizes the strategic benefits of Pakistan's partnership with China, it also highlights the potential risks of dependency. As Pakistan becomes more reliant on China

for economic and military support, its foreign policy options may become increasingly constrained (Rana, 2015). Realism suggests that such dependency can limit Pakistan's ability to pursue an independent foreign policy, as its actions may need to align with Chinese interests, particularly in the context of U.S.-China tensions. This strategic dependency is not without consequences. As U.S.-China rivalry intensifies, Pakistan may find itself in a precarious position, forced to revolve a complex geopolitical environment where its interests could be subordinated to the broader strategic objectives of China. Realists argue that while alliances are essential for survival in an anarchic world, they can also create vulnerabilities, especially when one state becomes overly dependent on another. (Walt, 1987).

Pakistan's alignment with U.S. and China: A historical analysis

Since the independence, Pakistan established a strategic alliance with the United States, demonstrated by its participation in U.S.-led alliances such as SEATO and CENTO during the 1950s (Jabeen & Mazhar, 2011). This alignment reached its zenith during the Eisenhower administration, as the United States sought strategic partners to contain the spread of communism during the Cold War (Javid & Mushtaq, 2014). The 1954 Mutual Defense Assistance Agreement, coupled with subsequent military and economic aid highlighted the depth of this alliance (Islam, 1983; Zaheer, November 09, 2021). This agreement formalized military cooperation between the two nations, with the United States providing substantial military assistance to bolster Pakistan's defense capabilities. The aid was meant not only at addressing immediate security concerns but also at fostering a long-term strategic partnership. The provision of military equipment, training and financial assistance significantly enhanced Pakistan's military capabilities, establishing it as a key player in the regional balance of power.

The formal establishment of diplomatic relations between Pakistan and China on May 21, 1951, marked a significant event, reflecting Pakistan's strategic shift towards diversifying its alliances (Zaho, 2022). A major turning point in this regard occurred in the 1960s, when Pakistan began to realign its foreign policy towards China. The Sino-Indian border conflict of 1962 played a pivotal role in this shift. As tensions between China and India escalated over territorial disputes, Pakistan found itself strategically aligned with China (Javid Umbreen & Jahangir, 2015). The conflict served as a catalyst for Pakistan to reassess its regional alliances and rethink its foreign policy objectives.

The Tashkent Agreement of 1966, which expected to resolve the Indo-Pakistani War of 1965 made further tense relations between Pakistan and the United States. Despite being a key ally, the United States' perceived support for India during the Tashkent negotiations contributed to a growing sense of unease among Pakistan's higher authorities. This incident fueled Pakistan's inclination towards seeking alternative alliances, leading to a closer association with China (Lalwani, March 2023). Geopolitics witnessed another shift with U.S. President Richard Nixon's visit to China in 1972 and the subsequent thaw in U.S.-China relations. Pakistan, acting as an intermediary, facilitated this historic rapprochement, contributing to a new geopolitical scene (Gilani, 2006; Baluch, 2006) (Baloch, 2006; Gilani, 2006). However, the normalization of U.S.-China relations did not restore the previous warmth in U.S.-Pakistan relations, as the dynamics had fundamentally changed.

The 1980s saw a resurgence of the Pakistan-U.S alliance during the Afghan-Soviet War. The Soviet aggression to Afghanistan in 1979 prompted the United States, under President Reagan, to view Pakistan as a crucial partner in resisting Soviet forces. Military and financial support from the U.S. flowed into Pakistan,

particularly during the Zia-ul-Haq era, marking another phase of alignment with the United States. U.S. assistance to the Afghan mujahideen, channeled through Pakistan, solidified their strategic partnership during this period (Hilali, 2017). However, this alliance had significant long-term repercussions for Pakistan. The influx of military aid and foreign fighters, initially intended to support the Afghan resistance, led to the growth of militant groups within Pakistan (Shahbaz, 2023). The support provided to Afghan mujahideen contributed to the rise of factions that later turned against Pakistan, leading to internal conflicts and security challenges. The enduring consequences include persistent terrorism, internal instability and a strained security environment. Furthermore, after the Cold War the changing dynamics in U.S. foreign policy strained bilateral relations, creating complexities in Pakistan's future geopolitical alignments (Hilali A. Z., 2002).

In the 1990s, following the end of the Cold War, Pakistan was compelled to reassess its diplomatic relationships amid a reshaping global political situation. Its longstanding alliance with the United States underwent a shift as U.S. priorities evolved (Zaidi & Saud, 2021). The nuclear tests conducted by both Pakistan and India in 1998 led to the imposition of sanctions by the United States, further straining bilateral relations (Tahira, 2022). This diplomatic isolation posed significant challenges for Pakistan, prompting it to seek alternative partnerships, most notably with China. The decision to tilt towards China was based on well-considered factors. Economically, China offered Pakistan avenues for development, trade and investment, which were crucial during a period of international sanctions (Liu & Ahmad, February 25, 2020). China's rise as a global economic powerhouse presented opportunities that Pakistan could not afford to ignore. Strategically, aligning with China provided Pakistan with a reliable partner

in a region characterized by uncertain dynamics. China's growing influence in global affairs made it an attractive ally for Pakistan.

The strengthening of ties between Pakistan and China during the late 1990s laid the foundation for a deeper alignment that has persisted into the 21st century (Hussai et al., 2020) (Hussain et al., 2020). This strategic recalibration was not merely about finding a new ally; it reflected Pakistan's adaptability in response to changing geopolitical realities. The strategic partnership with China has since become a cornerstone of Pakistan's foreign policy, offering economic collaboration, military cooperation and diplomatic support (Kumar, 2006).

The 21st century saw a further extending of Pakistan's alignment with China. The launch of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) in 2015 stands out as a significant milestone (Dawn, April 20, 2015). This infrastructure and economic development project, part of China's Belt and Road Initiative, has become a cornerstone of the China-Pakistan partnership (Wolf, 2020) (Wolf, 2020). The deepening economic ties, demonstrated by massive Chinese investments in Pakistani infrastructure and energy projects, highlight Pakistan's strategic realignment towards China in recent years. Several factors have been instrumental in shaping Pakistan's geopolitical alignments. Geopolitical considerations, driven by security concerns related to India, have consistently played a pivotal role. Economic interests, represented by the transformative impact of CPEC on Pakistan's economic perspectives have become increasingly prominent (Arshad & Haidong, 2017). Shifts in the global balance of power, particularly the rise of China as a global power, have also influenced Pakistan's alignment choices. Moreover, scholars have emphasized the significance of domestic politics and leadership changes in shaping the course of Pakistan's foreign policy decisions (Raashed & Anwar, November 20, 2020).

China-U.S rivalry and Pakistan

Pakistan, strategically located at the crossroads of South Asia, Central Asia and the Middle East that is a key spot within the evolving geostrategic environment. The country's strategic analysts are acutely aware of the ongoing tensions between China and the United States, recognizing the potential implications for Pakistan's relationships with both global powers. The United States is a Pakistan's primary export market and a preferred educational destination for the nation's elite. In contrast, China has emerged as Pakistan's principal supplier of arms and has established unparalleled economic collaboration through the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC), a project valued at an estimated \$62 billion (Afzal, June 2020).

A key manifestation of the U.S.-China competition is the "U.S. pivot to the Indo-Pacific, a strategy intended at counterbalancing China's influence (Chen, 2013)". Events such as the U.S.-China trade war and disputes over the South China Sea have heightened tensions, contributing to the complexities of the region (Kim, October 22, 2023; Zaheer D. M., 2023, p. 48). China's assertiveness in territorial disputes, coupled with its Belt and Road Initiative, has further fueled concerns among neighboring countries. This evolving dynamic forces countries like Pakistan to steer the delicate balance between the two superpowers.

This situation suggests that Pakistani policymakers must adopt a prudent strategy in managing bilateral relations with both China and the United States, avoiding any inclination to align exclusively with one side (Ali, 2020). Pakistan's decisions on this geopolitical chessboard have direct implications for the regional

balance of power. Alignment with China provides Beijing with a strategic foothold in South Asia; while Pakistan is historical, ties with the United States continue to shape American interests in the region (Siddiqi, 2022; Afzaal, March 2022). The burgeoning alignment between India and the United States, intended at countering Chinese influence in the Indo-Pacific, has drawn significant attention in Islamabad, introducing both opportunities and challenges for Pakistan (Ranter, 2016). The intensifying rivalry between China and the United States has the potential to exacerbate the longstanding India-Pakistan conflict, potentially leading to an arms race and heightened intelligence capabilities on both sides, driven by the broader U.S.-China competition (Siddiqi, 2022). The Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi's decision in August 2019 to revoke the special status of Kashmir and Ladakh heightened tensions among India, China, and Pakistan along the contested Himalayan borders. The continuing border standoff between China and India offers Pakistan a chance to challenge India in partnership with China. However, this reactive strategy also provides Washington with an opportunity to strengthen its relationship with New Delhi in its border disputes with China. Washington's Indo-Pacific strategy, initially focused on maritime cooperation, has expanded to assist India in addressing continental challenges posed by China, which holds significant implications for Pakistan. Although an abrupt shift in the region's dynamics is currently unlikely, recent announcements following the U.S.-India Dialogue about the United States sharing geospatial intelligence and advanced missile technology with India have raised concerns in Pakistan. India's primary objective in enhancing its strategic alliances with the United States is to ultimately position itself as a regional superpower, while the United States aspires to see India's economic growth surpass that of China (Madan, June 23, 2017).

The U.S.-China strategic competition also significantly affects Pakistan's relations with Iran. Both global powers have divergent views on Iran, with the United States imposing sanctions and withdrawing from the Iran nuclear deal, thereby straining its ties with Tehran. In contrast, China maintains robust diplomatic relations with Iran, condemning U.S. policies and fostering cooperation. Despite challenges such as U.S. and Indian opposition to projects like CPEC and the impact of economic sanctions on Pakistan-Iran relations, the strategic location of the Gwadar seaport has the potential to enhance economic relations between Iran, Pakistan and China. Initiatives such as the proposed connection of Chabahar and Gwadar through highways and the construction of the Iran-Pakistan gas pipeline are under discussion, which could foster trilateral trade relations. However, these efforts face significant challenges, including regional security concerns related to terrorism, political instability and opposition to CPEC from the United States and India (Zaheer D. M., January 25, 2023).

China's initiation of CPEC can be understood as a strategic response to the U.S. Pivot to Asia policy, reflecting a countermeasure directed at mitigating U.S. influence in the region, particularly in relation to India. The evolving dynamics of major power rivalry have prompted China to assert its geopolitical interests in South Asia through transformative initiatives like CPEC, which offer significant economic benefits for Pakistan. However, the success of CPEC is threatened not only by India but also by the United States. The economic upliftment anticipated from CPEC presents a new challenge for India, which has faced difficulties in isolating Pakistan on various international platforms concerning terrorism and extremism (Madan, June 23, 2017). Moreover, Pakistan's involvement in the CPEC flagship program of China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) has led to improved relations with Russia. In 2014, there was a notable improvement in

relations between Russia and Pakistan, culminating in an agreement for military exercises, which were eventually conducted in 2016. Beyond the normalization of military-to-military contacts, both countries have expressed a willingness to connect South Asia with the Eurasian landmass through CPEC (Marwat, August 18, 202). For Pakistan, Russia presents an opportunity to balance its foreign policy, particularly in the context of strengthening security arrangements between India and the United States.

On November 4, 2019, former U.S. President Donald Trump unveiled the Blue Dot Network during the 35th Asian Summit in Bangkok, Thailand. The initiative, supported by the United States, Australia, Japan and later India on February 25, 2020, aims to attract global investors to contribute to infrastructure development worldwide. India's active participation in the initiative is crucial, significantly contributing to its economic development plans. Additionally, it positions India to compete with and potentially surpass China and other nations, thereby strengthening its global standing through the Blue Dot Network (Bibi, 2023). Recent developments, including the U.S. withdrawal from Afghanistan and the resulting geopolitical changes in South Asia, have added further complexity to the region's dynamics. Pakistan's involvement in mediating peace talks between the Afghan government and the Taliban, coupled with its careful balancing between China and the United States, highlights the sophisticated nature of its geopolitical strategies (Mohan, August 22, 2021). As China and the United States engage in reactive strategies and countermeasures, Pakistan's strategic choices become increasingly critical. The geopolitical shifts resulting from the U.S. withdrawal from Afghanistan have significant implications not only for Pakistan's regional influence but also for its economic ties and security considerations (Sarwar & Siraj, 2021).

Pakistan-SCO and US-China Rivalry

The formation of the SCO was the result of negotiations between the Central Asian Republics (CARs) and China, occurring during a period when both China and Russia were navigating their democratic recovery, while the CARs faced significant challenges related to state-building and border security (Khetran & Khalid, 2019). The SCO was officially established in 2001 in response to shared security and military concerns, especially those related to border areas. Key drivers for its formation included the rise of religious extremism, international terrorism and ethnic separatism. Over time, the SCO expanded its scope to encompass economic development and regional stability, promoting a shared identity and cooperation on issues of mutual concern (Irfan et al., May 2017).

Although not a full member, the United States secured observer status within the SCO, allowing it to participate in meetings. The U.S. has consistently expressed concerns regarding regional security, particularly in relation to Afghanistan and Central Asia, which aligns with the SCO's focus on addressing security challenges (Ziegler, 2013). Despite lacking voting rights, the U.S. has actively pursued cooperation within the SCO framework, particularly in the domain of counterterrorism initiatives. In 2017, Pakistan and India were granted permanent membership in the SCO, with China supporting Pakistan and Russia backing India (Habib & Zhu, January 22, 2020). This expansion marked a significant milestone, enhancing regional integration and strengthening the SCO's influence in Central and South Asia.

Pakistan's involvement in the SCO reflects a strategic balancing act in its relations with both China and the United States. The complex history of Pakistan-U.S. relations in the post-9/11 era provides essential context for understanding

Pakistan's role within the SCO (Khan, October 26, 2020). The multilayers nature of these ties is evident in various instances of collaboration, particularly in counterterrorism efforts. However, tensions have occasionally arisen due to divergent interests, especially concerning Afghanistan and issues related to nuclear proliferation. Pakistan strategically leverages its SCO membership to balance these alliances, utilizing the organization as a diplomatic bridge to engage with both China and the United States simultaneously. This delicate balancing act highlights Pakistan's capacity to navigate the complex dynamics of the U.S.-China rivalry.

Pakistan's membership in the SCO contributes significantly to regional stability amidst the ongoing U.S.-China rivalry. Collaborative efforts within the SCO framework, particularly through the Regional Counter-Terrorism Structure (RCTS), play a vital role in enhancing stability in South Asia (Foot, 2006) (Foot, 2006). Pakistan's involvement in intelligence-sharing, joint exercises and other counterterrorism initiatives within the SCO strengthens its ability to address regional security threats (Wallace, December 13, 2014). These joint initiatives and conflict resolution mechanisms provide a platform for member nations, including Pakistan, to collectively address regional challenges. However, concerns have been raised about the potential for the SCO to become a proxy battleground for U.S.-China competition, with their respective allies vying for influence within the organization, thereby posing challenges to regional stability (Sharma, 2021).

Participation in the SCO enhances Pakistan's regional influence, strategically positioning it between the spheres of influence of China and the United States. Membership in the SCO establishes Pakistan as a key player, enabling it to contribute actively to the regional discourse. Alignment with China bolsters Pakistan's regional standing, offering opportunities for significant policy contributions. Concurrently, Pakistan uses its involvement in the SCO to maintain

influence with the United States, demonstrating diplomatic finesse and participating in initiatives aligned with U.S. interests (Khetran & Khalid, 2019). This strategic balance positions Pakistan as a crucial actor, effectively leveraging its SCO membership to exert influence on multiple fronts.

Conclusion:

The U.S.-China rivalry affects Pakistan's geopolitical positioning. As the competition between these two global powers intensifies, Pakistan finds itself strategically navigating between its historical alliance with the United States and its deepening partnership with China especially through the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). This balancing act is critical for Pakistan as it seeks to maintain its national interests amidst external pressures. Pakistan's strategic decisions, influenced by realism and historical context, impact regional stability and the broader power dynamics within South Asia. The complex interaction of security concerns, economic dependencies and shifting global alliances highlights Pakistan's challenging position in the evolving geostrategic scene.

References

- Afzaal, M. (March 2022). *The China-Pakistan economic corridor of the Belt and Road Initiative concept, context and assessment. Book Review, 691-805.*
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/13602381.2020.1738075>
- Afzal, M. (June 2020). "At all costs": How Pakistan and China control the narrative on the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor. Retrieved from Brookings: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/at-all-costs-how-pakistan-and-china-control-the-narrative-on-the-china-pakistan-economic-corridor/>
- Ain, Q. u. (May 24, 2023). *US China Rivalry and South Asia 24 May 2023. ISSRA.*
<https://doi.org/https://www.ndu.edu.pk/issra/pub/post-seminar-report/US-China-Rivalry-and-South-Asia-PSR.pdf>

- Ali, S. (2020). *The U.S.-China Strategic Rivalry and its Implications for Pakistan. Geopolitics of the Indo- Pacific*. <https://doi.org/https://www.stimson.org/2020/the-u-s-china-strategic-rivalry-and-its-implications-for-pakistan/>
- Anam, A., Abasi, A. M., Rashieed, A., & Bukhari, S. (2022). *Global Power Dynamics And Pakistan's Foreign Policy*. *Multicultural Education*, 8(9), 64-77. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7139785>
- Anwar, S. M. (2020). *Relevance and Significance of Pak-China Relationship for USA in Changing Regional Dynamics*. *Journal of law & Social science*, 2(2), 87-95.
- Arshad, M. U., & Haidong, Z. (2017). *China-Pakistan economic corridor (CPEC) issues/barrier and imperatives of Pakistan and China*. *Journal of Global Business Insights*, 02(02), 104-114. <https://doi.org/10.5038/2640-6489.2.2.1023>
- Baluch, Q. B. (2006). *Engagement and estrangement in US-Pakistan relations*. *The Dialogue*, 01(04), 28-56.
- Bibi, S. (2023). *US-CHINA ECONOMIC RIVALRY AND ITS IMPACTS ON PAKISTAN'S ECONOMY*. *Global Journal of Humanities and Science*, 02(02), 01-15. <https://doi.org/10.59129/gjhssr.v2.i2.2023.18>
- Chen, R. (2013). *A Critical Analysis of the U.S. "Pivot" toward the Asia-Pacific: How Realistic is Neo-realism?* *Connections*, 12(03), 39-64. <https://doi.org/https://www.jstor.org/stable/26326331>
- Dawn. (April 20, 2015). *Xi Jinping's warm welcome in Pakistan*. Retrieved from DAWN.COM: <https://www.dawn.com/news/1177125>
- Foot, R. (2006). *Chinese strategies in a US-hegemonic global order: accommodating and hedging*. *International Affairs*, 82(01), 77-94. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2346.2006.00516.x>
- Gilani, T. (2006). *US-Pakistan relations: the way forward*. *The US Army War College Quarterly: Parameters*, 36(4).
- Habib, N., & Zhu, H. Y. (January 22, 2020). *What CPEC Means for China's Middle East Relations*. *The Diplomat*. <https://doi.org/https://thediplomat.com/2020/01/what-pec-means-for-chinas-middle-east-relations/>
- Hilali, A. Z. (2002). *The costs and benefits of the Afghan War for Pakistan*. *Contemporary South Asia*, 11(3), 291-310. *Contemporary South Asia*, 11(3), 291-310.
- Hilali, A. Z. (2017). *US-Pakistan relationship: Soviet invasion of Afghanistan*. Taylor & francis. Routledge. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315235165>
- Hussai, I., Hussain, I., & Qambari, I. H. (2020). *History of Pakistan-China Relations: The Complex*

Interdependence Theory. The Chinese Historical Review, 27(02), 146-164.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/1547402X.2020.1831176>

- Irfan, M., Iqbal, M., Iqbal, A., Iqbal, Z., Riaz, R. A., & Mehmood, A. (May 2017). Opportunities and challenges in control of smart grids – Pakistani perspective. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 71, 652-674. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2016.12.095>
- Islam, M. (1983). Pakistan-US New Connection: An Evaluation. *Pakistan Horizon*, 36(03), 31-44.
- Jabeen, M., & Mazhar, M. S. (2011). SECURITY GAME: SEATO and CENTO as Instrument of Economic and Military Assistance to Encircle Pakistan. *Pakistan Economic and Social Review*, 49(01), 109-132.
- Javid Umbreen, & Jahangir, M. (2015). Pakistan-China strategic relationship: A glorious journey of 55 years. *Journal of the Research Society of Pakistan*, 52(01).
- Javid, U., & Mushtaq, I. (2014). Historical perspective of Pakistan USA Relations; Lessons for Pakistan. *South Asian Studies*. *South Asian Studies*, 2901, 291-304.
- Jervis, R. (1978). Cooperation Under the Security Dilemma. *World Politics*, 30(02), 167-214.
- Khan, H. (October 26, 2020). China, the emerging economic power: options and repercussions for Pak-US relations. *International Politics*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1057/s41311-020-00265-1>
- Khetran, M. S., & Khalid, M. H. (2019). The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor: Gateway to Central Asia. *World Scientific*, 05(03), 455-469. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1142/S2377740019500179>
- Kim, H. J. (October 22, 2023). South Korea, US and Japan hold first-ever trilateral aerial exercise in face of North Korean threats. Retrieved from AP: <https://apnews.com/article/south-korea-japan-us-aerial-drills-fc04a9b22a04b118d774ed70837b7aeb>
- Kumar, A. (2006). China-Pakistan economic relations. *Institute of Peace and Conflict Studies*. Research Report. <https://doi.org/https://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep09263>
- Lalwani, S. P. (March 2023). A Threshold Alliance: The China-Pakistan. UNITED STATES INSTITUTE OF PEACE www.usip.org.
- Liu, A. H., & Ahmad, R. Q. (February 25, 2020). The Changing Dynamics and New Developments of China-Pakistan Relations. *India Quarterly: A Journal of International Affairs*, 76(01). <https://doi.org/.org/10.1177/0974928419901195>
- Madan, T. (June 23, 2017). When Modi meets Trump: Where do U.S.-India relations stand? Retrieved from Brookings: <https://www.brookings.edu/articles/when-modi-meets-trump-where-do-u-s-india-relations-stand/>
- Marwat, Z. K. (August 18, 202). Pak-Russia growing relationship. Retrieved from The

News: <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/702237-pak-russia-growing-relationship>

*Mearsheimer, J. J. (2001). *The Tragedy of Great Power Politics*. W.W. Norton & Company.*

- Mendelson, P. (March 20, 2014). *The First Rule Of Survival*. Goodreads.
- Mohan, V. (August 22, 2021). *Changing Political Dynamics in South Asia: The Belt and Road Initiative and Its Effects on Indian Regional Hegemony*. *Journal of Indo-Pacific Affairs*. <https://doi.org/https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/JIPA/Display/Article/2743694/changing-political-dynamics-in-south-asia-the-belt-and-road-initiative-and-its/>
- Pant, H. V. (2012). *The US-India Nuclear Pact: Policy, Process, and Great Power Politics*. Oxford University Press.
- Raashed, M., & Anwar, R. (November 20, 2020). *Pakistan's Foreign Policy In Transition: Perspectives*(17).
- Rana, M. (2015). *Dependency and Security: Pakistan's Relations with China*. *Asian Affairs*, 41(01), 102-118.
- Ranter, E. (2016). *Rebalancing to Asia with an*. *The Washington Quarterly*, 36(02), 21-38. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/0163660X.2013.791080>
- Sarwar, F., & Siraj, U. (2021). *Afghan Peace Process: Regional Complexities and the Role of China*. *NUST Journal of International Peace & Stability*, 04(01), 40-52. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.37540/njips.v4i1.78>
- Shahbaz, M. (2023). *Revisiting Friends & Foes: US-Pak Relation's Turbulent History and Future*. *Scientific Research*, 13(01). <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojps.2023.131006>
- Sharma, B. K. (2021). *Geopolitics in Central Asia*. *Indian Foreign Affairs Journal*, 16(04), 322-330.
- Siddiqi, F. H. (2022). *US Indo-Pacific Strategy and Pakistan's Foreign Policy: The Hedging Option*. *Strategic Studies*, 42(01), 01-16.
- Siddique, S. (2021). *CPEC and the Strategic Implications for South Asia*. *South Asian Journal of International Relations*, 04(01), 89-105.
- Tahira, I. (2022). *Pakistan under the Shadow of Nuclear Power: Scoping the Beneficiaries of US Aid, Effectiveness, and Future Implications*. *Pakistan Social Sciences Review*, 06(01), 40-52.
- Wallace, T. (December 13, 2014). *China and the Regional Counter-Terrorism Structure: An Organizational Analysis*. 199-220. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/14799855.2014.976614>
- Walt, S. M. (1987). *The Origins of Alliances*. Cornell University Press.
- Waltz, K. N. (1979). *Theory of International Politics*. McGraw-Hill.

Wolf, S. O. (2020). *The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor of the Belt and Road Initiative*. Springer.

Zaheer, D. M. (2023). *Geopolitical Conflicts: A Quest to Understand the Struggle of Influenc.*

www.rmrpublishers.org.

Zaheer, D. M. (January 25, 2023). *The strategic vista of Chabahar Port*. Retrieved from *Pakistan Observer*: <https://pakobserver.net/the-strategic-vista-of-chabahar-port-by-dr-muhammad-akram-zaheer/>

Zaheer, D. M. (November 09, 2021). *China's foreign policy towards Pakistan and India*. Retrieved from *Pakistan Today*: <https://www.pakistantoday.com.pk/2021/11/09/chinas-foreign-policy-towards-pakistan-and-india/>

Zaho, J. (2022). *The development of China-Pakistan diplomatic relations*. <https://rclss.com/pij/article/view/284>. *Cross-Cultural Relations between China and Pakistan*, 06(01). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.55014/pij.v6iSI.284>

Zaidi, S. M., & Saud, A. (2021). *From "Geo-Strategic Rivals" to "Probable Allies"? A Constructivist Analysis of the Pakistan–Russia Relations*. *Herald of the Russian Academy of Sciences*, 91, 53-163.

Ziegler, C. E. (2013). *Central Asia, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization, and American Foreign Policy*. *Asian Survey*, 53(03), 481-505. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1525/as.2013.53.3.484>